

EPOXY-GRAPHITE OXIDE NANO COMPOSITES

R. Mikael Larsen

Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, Aalborg University
Fibigerstræde 16, DK-9220 Aalborg East, Denmark

Email: rml@m-tech.aau.dk web page: <http://www.m-tech.aau.dk>

Keywords: Epoxy, graphite oxide, graphene, nanocomposites, mechanical properties

ABSTRACT

Graphite oxide produced by Hummers method is added to epoxy for strengthening purpose. Generally the E-modulus was increased due to the graphite oxide addition, however, depending on the treatment of the graphite oxide an increase or decrease was observed for the glass transition temperature. Addition of graphite oxide generally initially increased the curing speed; however, the final curing degree was lower.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene and many graphene derived carbon compounds like carbon nanotubes have excellent mechanical properties and high electrical and thermal conductance. Graphene, as nanofillers, are used to improve mechanical properties and produce electrical conducting polymers. Due to the much lower price the focus in the research have during the last years shifted from carbon nanotubes towards graphene. Graphene have further advantages as it also make the polymer more flame retardant and decreases the gas permeation.[1]

Graphene can be produced by various methods, where reduction of graphite oxide is the dominant route to produce graphene in large quantities.[2] Graphite oxide is produced from graphite subjected to strong water-free oxidizing agents.[3] The graphite oxide contains many different carbonyl groups, such as carboxylic, hydroxyl and epoxide groups.[4] In thermosets like epoxy these groups might form covalent bonds to the polymer system.

Most experimental works study nano composites with graphene produced by several methods including reduction of graphite oxide (GO). This is partly because the GO is unstable and start to decompose at temperatures as low as 100°C but also because GO is electrically insulating so for the purpose of producing electrically conducting polymer reduced GO must be used.

X.Hu et al produced epoxy nanocomposites with dopamine reduced graphite oxide (DPA-GO). Adding 1 phr DPA-GO increased the storage modulus and the glass transition temperature.[5] L. Tang investigated the effect of dispersion of thermally reduced GO on the mechanical properties of epoxy nanocomposites containing up to 0.2 wt-% reduced GO.[6] N. Yousefi et al. have compared the incorporation of unreduced and in-situ reduced GO in an epoxy resin. They found superior strengthening of the in-situ reduced GO compared to the unreduced.[7]

In this paper graphite oxide will be added to epoxy in order to form covalent bonds and integrating the graphite oxide into the epoxy network. The epoxy is a low temperature curing type of epoxy, so it is assumed that no decomposition is taking place during the curing. It is documented that amines can react with the epoxide groups on the GO.[8] The focus will be on the final mechanical properties of the composite material.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Fabrication of graphite nanofiller

Graphite oxide is produced by a modified Hummers method.[9] 40 ml H_2SO_4 + 6.6 ml HNO_3 is mixed in a 150 ml beaker and cooled in ice-water bath. Stirring is maintained during the whole time. 1 gr. of graphite is added and is stirred for 30 min. 6 gr $KMnO_4$ is added slowly to avoid excess heating. Ice is removed from ice-water bath and mixture is slowly allowed to heat to room temperature. Mixture is slowly heated to 40°C for >1h. Water was added slowly to the mixture up to ~6-800 ml. 10 ml of 30% H_2O_2 is added slowly with stirring and the solution become yellowish-brown. Suspension sediments until next day and excess solution are decanted and new water up to 6-800 ml is added. The mixture was bath sonicated for 1h and ultra-centrifuged to remove water. The addition of water, bath sonication and ultra-centrifuged was repeated several times. After this ethanol was used instead of water and cleansing with ethanol was repeated twice. After ultracentrifugation GO-EtOH was achieved. No drying was done as it was observed that dispersion in solvents afterward was problematic if the sample had been dried.

GO-EtOH was modified by reaction with the epoxy resin i.e. Bisphenol A/F Diglycidyl Ether according to the recipe by A. Eitan et al. [10] The GO-EtOH was dispersed in acetone and resin 117 was added. Some NaOH was added as a catalyst and the mixture were heated to 70°C for 1 h for the GO-EtOH to react with the resin. The mixture was cleansed three times with ultra-sonication in acetone followed by ultracentrifugation, and finally once in tetrahydrofuran. The modified GO is called GO-117 in the paper.

2.2 Epoxy composites fabrication

The nanocomposites were fabricated using the respective GO and a commercial epoxy Proset-117 / 229PF. The epoxy resin Proset 117 contains 30-60% Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A (DGEBA), 30-60% Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F resin, and 10-30% butanendioldiglycidyl ether. The epoxy hardener Proset 229PF contains 60-100% Polyoxypropyleneamine and 10-30% Methylene-di(cyclohexylamine). The mixing ratio is 100:34 by weight. This epoxy is used for infusion processes and has a viscosity of 220 mPa s at 25°C right after mixing.

The required amount of graphite oxide were dispersed in acetone for 0.5 h using an 80 W ultrasonic rod generator to form a suspension; an ice bath was used to keep the suspension cold during sonication. The nanotube suspension was then poured into 100 parts by weight of epoxy resin, and ultra-shear mixed for 30 min. Afterwards the acetone was evaporated at 45 °C until all the solvent were evaporated which was proved by weighing the blend. The epoxy equivalent was measured according to ISO 3001. For the neat epoxy the resin/hardener ratio is 100:34; knowing the epoxy equivalent of the resin and the mixtures it is possible to calculate the right resin/hardener ratio for the mixtures as shown in Table 1. After adding the hardener the GO / resin mixture were stirred under vacuum to prevent introduction of air bubbles. Dog bone test specimens (ISO 527-2, specimens type 1BA) was obtained by casting the resin/hardener mixture in a silicon mould, specimens was pre-cured at room temperature for 24 h and post cured at 80 °C or 120°C for 16 h. The cured samples were 80 mm long, 4.8 mm wide and 2-3 mm thick. The samples were finally grinded to a uniform sample thickness of approx. 1.4 mm.

Table 1. Epoxy equivalents for the resin with GO.

	Resin 117	Resin 117 + 1% GO-EtOH	Resin 117 + 3% GO-EtOH	Resin 117 + 1% GO-117	Resin 117 + 3% GO-117
Epoxy equivalent	170	193	230	173	180
Resin/hardener ratio	100:34	100:30	100:25	100:33	100:32

2.3 Tensile testing

For the tensile testing the grinded samples were used. The measured data are the average of five samples. The tensile testing machine was a Zwick Z100 equipped with a 5 kN loadcell and an incremental clip-on extensometer. The strain rate was 1 mm/min.

2.4 DSC – glass transition temperature

The glass transition temperature and possible post curing of the SWNT reinforced epoxy composites were measured with Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) using TA Q2000 instrument. The measurements were performed in a nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 3°C/min using modulated DSC $\pm 0.35^\circ\text{C}$ every 45 sec. The samples were heated from 20°C to 250°C, then cooled to 20°C and second time heated to 200°C. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was measured as the inflection point on the reversing heat flow curve of three samples.

2.5 Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

The storage and loss modulus and glass transition temperature (T_g) of the SWNT reinforced epoxy composites were measured with TA Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) Q800 instrument operating in the three point bending mode at an frequency of 1.0 Hz, strain amplitude of 100 μm and sample length (i.e. distance between supports) of 50 mm. Sample dimension were: length: ~60 mm, width: ~4.8 mm and height: ~1,4 mm. The data were collected from ambient to 100 °C at a scanning rate of 3 °C /min. The glass transition temperature was measured as the peak value of the loss modulus.

2.6 DSC – curing behaviour

The curing behaviour of the epoxy – graphite oxide mixtures were measured with (DSC) TA Q2000 instrument with the weight of the sample being about 7 mg. The measurements were performed under a nitrogen atmosphere. The samples were heated from 25°C to 80°C at 60°C/min and held at 80°C for 1200 min. Then the sample were cooled to 0°C and second time heated to 200°C with a heating and cooling rate of 20°C/min to measure the glass transition temperature and possibly heat of post curing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties (Tensile testing)

Table 2 Mechanical properties of the cured neat epoxy and the epoxy composites

	E-modulus [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Fracture strain [%]
Cured at 80°C			
Neat epoxy	3186±183	62.8±1.7	6.2±0.6
Epoxy + 1% GO-EtOH	3405±137	66.5±1.1	3.8±1.8
Epoxy + 3% GO-EtOH	3108±330	58.7±8.2	5.6±0.8
Epoxy + 1% GO-117	3878±130	67.0±2.9	3.2±0.7
Epoxy + 3% GO-117	3749±143	66.5±6.3	2.7±0.7
Cured at 120°C			
Neat epoxy	3297±96	60.0±1.3	6.4±0.6
Epoxy + 1% GO-EtOH	3444±221	60.2±2.7	4.0±1.0
Epoxy + 3% GO-EtOH	3358±325	62.0±2.1	3.6±0.4
Epoxy + 1% GO-117	3933±290	62.4±1.1	3.8±0.4
Epoxy + 3% GO-117	3651±251	64.6±0.8	4.1±1.5

Adding 3% GO either as GO-EtOH or GO-117 increases the E-modulus with 22% for GO-EtOH and 16% for GO-117 as can be seen in Table 2. Despite the lower degree of curing for the sample with GO-EtOH the largest stiffness is seen with these samples, however the standard deviation is large so the difference between GO-EtOH and GO-117 is not significant. Looking at the strength the conclusion is not clear partly due to the large standard deviation of the strength values. There might be an increase in tensile strength when 3% GO-EtOH or GO-117 is added. Adding 1% GO-EtOH seems to give a significant increase in the tensile strength; the reason for the behaviour is unknown. The addition of GO, however, gives a significant decrease in the fracture strain. The standard deviation is generally large indicating that large agglomerates are the cause of the reduced ductility. Looking at the micrographs in Figure 1 the GO is generally well dispersed on a macroscopic point of view. But the size of the GO agglomerates seems to be tenths of micron large. The dispersion is similar to the dispersion observed in other works. [6] In these works better dispersion was achieved by using either a surfactant or ball milling of the graphene nanosheets. Generally increasing the curing temperature to 120°C gives no significant change in the mechanical properties.

Figure 1. LOM micrographs of the GO epoxy composite with 3% GO. The samples were $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$ thick.

3.2 DMA and DSC

Figure 2. Storage modulus as function of temperature for samples cured at 80°C.

Figure 3. Loss modulus as function of temperature for samples cured at 80°C.

Generally the storage modulus at RT increases as a function of the added amount of GO. However epoxy with 3% GO-EtOH softens at significantly lower temperatures than the other samples irrespective of the curing temperature. This is in agreement with the glass transition temperatures shown in Table 3. Adding GO-117 however increases the glass transition temperature and the stiffness is retained at higher temperatures. Adding 3% GO-117 results in the best stiffness at high temperature. As can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 4 adding GO results in an incomplete curing at 80°C. From Figure 5 it is clear that curing at 120°C gives a full curing; however, glass transition temperature and the storage modulus are not affected which is evident from Table 3.

Figure 4. DSC total heat flow for samples cured at 80°C heated from room temperature at constant heating rate of 3°C/min.

Figure 5. DSC total heat flow for samples cured at 120°C heated from room temperature at constant heating rate of 3°C/min.

Table 3. Glass transition temperature from DSC and DMA measurements together with residual heat and the storage modulus.

	DSC		DMA	
	T _g [°C]	Residual heat [J/g]	Storage modulus @ 25°C [MPa]	T _g @ peak loss modulus [°C]
Cured at 80°C				
Neat epoxy	61	0	3304	60.5
Epoxy + 1% GO-EtOH	64	20.4	3612	59.5
Epoxy + 3% GO-EtOH	56	40.1	3736	55.8
Epoxy + 1% GO-117	67	17.8	3535	62.8
Epoxy + 3% GO-117	67	32.7	3856	63.6
Cured at 120°C				
Neat epoxy	64	0	3323	61.6
Epoxy + 1% GO-EtOH	60	0	3510	61.6
Epoxy + 3% GO-EtOH	52	2.6	3819	55.7
Epoxy + 1% GO-117	65	0	3376	62.8
Epoxy + 3% GO-117	63	0	3734	63.3

3.3 Curing behaviour

Figure 6. DSC heat flow measured and the integrated heat flow (ΔH) during curing at 80°C of the samples.

In Figure 6 is shown the heat flow and the integrated heat flow i.e. the enthalpy due to the curing reaction and the heat of curing peaks at a higher value for the epoxy with 3% GO-EtOH, but the heat flow decays very fast and is after few minutes lower than epoxy without GO-EtOH. The fast decay can be triggered by the rapid increase in viscosity causing the reaction gradually to be more diffusion controlled. Looking at the enthalpy of curing it is clear that the addition of GO-EtOH results in less epoxy bonding being formed which is expected for the blend with less hardener. Adding GO-117 results also in a slightly increased viscosity during the initial stages of curing probably resulting in less curing, but no catalytic effect can be seen. After the isothermal curing at 80°C the samples were heated to 250°C at 10°C/min to see if any post curing took place. Addition of GO results in incomplete curing and some post curing take place during the heating to 200°C which can be seen from the data in Table 4. Adding the heat of post curing to the heat of curing during the isothermal step it can be seen that addition of GO-117 can result in a cross linking density very close to the neat epoxy, whereas addition of GO-EtOH will result in a lower cross linking density. Using the normal amount of hardener for the epoxy-3% GO-EtOH did not improve neither the mechanical properties nor the cross linking density, which will be reported in a future article. S. Qiu et al using a very different epoxy system (N,N,N',N'-tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone (DDS)) also noticed a catalytic effect of the curing when adding up to 5 wt-% GO to however they noticed no effect of the final degree of curing.[11]

Table 4. DSC measurements giving enthalpy of curing and the post curing and glass transition temperature after curing at 80°C for 1200 min.

	ΔH_{total} at 80°C isothermal curing [J/g]	Residual heat [J/g]	Tg after isothermal curing
Neat epoxy	498.4	-	66.7°C
Epoxy + 3% GO-117	464.9	18.9	68.0°C
Epoxy + 3% GO-EtOH 100:26	377.6	27.9	53.9°C

4 CONCLUSION

Adding GO-filler to epoxy increases the E-modulus and storage modulus at room temperature. However the fracture toughness decreases probably due to presence of GO-agglomerates.

Addition of unmodified GO accelerates the initial curing of the epoxy, however, also results in an incomplete curing. This might be explained by the higher viscosity of the sample causing the curing to be diffusion controlled at an earlier stage. It might also be caused by a decomposition of the GO during curing.

Adding GO generally lead to an increased epoxy equivalent leading to a lower resin/hardener ratio. The result is a lower cross linking density. Especially addition of unmodified GO with its large amounts of functional groups changes the epoxy equivalent of the resin mixture and results in lower cross bonding density and lower glass transition temperature and inferior storage modulus at higher temperature. The curing behaviour of epoxy with the modified graphite oxide (GO-117) is more similar to the curing behaviour of neat epoxy and the cured samples have higher storage modulus at higher temperature also compared to the neat epoxy.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Tapas Kuilla, Sambhu Bhadrab, Dahu Yaa, Nam Hoon Kim, Saswata Bose and Joong Hee Lee, "Recent advances in graphene based polymer composites", *Progress in Polymer Science*, 2010, 35, p.1350–1375
- [2] Rajatendu Sengupta, Mithun Bhattacharya, S. Bandyopadhyay and Anil K. Bhowmick, "A review on the mechanical and electrical properties of graphite and modified graphite reinforced polymer composites", *Progress in Polymer Science*, 2011, 36, p.638–670
- [3] Sungjin Park and Rodney S. Ruoff, "Chemical Methods for the Production of Graphenes", *Nature Nanotechnology*, 2009, 4, p.217-224
- [4] Anton Lerf, Heyong He, Michael Forster and Jacek Klinowski, "Structure of Graphite Oxide Revisited", *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 1998, 102, 4477-4482
- [5] Xinli Hu, Rongrong Qi, Jian Zhu, Jiaqi Lu, Yu Luo, Jieyu Jin, Pingkai Jiang, "Preparation and Properties of Dopamine Reduced Graphene Oxide and Its Composites of Epoxy", *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 2014, DOI: 10.1002/APP.39754
- [6] Long-Cheng Tang, Yan-Jun Wan, Dong Yan, Yong-Bing Pei, Li Zhao, Yi-Bao Li, Lian-Bin Wu, Jian-Xiong Jiang, Guo-Qiao Lai, "The effect of graphene dispersion on the mechanical properties of graphene/epoxy composites", *Carbon*, 2013, 60, p.16–27
- [7] Nariman Yousefi, Xiuyi Lin, Qingbin Zheng, Xi Shen, Jayaram R. Pothnis, Jingjing Jia, Eyal Zussman, Jang-Kyo Kim, "Simultaneous in situ reduction, self-alignment and covalent bonding in graphene oxide/epoxy composites", *Carbon*, 2013, 59, p.406–417
- [8] Athanasios B. Bourlinos, Dimitrios Gournis, Dimitrios Petridis, Tama's Szabo', Anna Szeri and Imre Dékány, "Graphite Oxide: Chemical Reduction to Graphite and Surface Modification with Primary Aliphatic Amines and Amino Acids", *Langmuir*, 2003, 19, p.6050-6055
- [9] Hummers W, Offeman R., "Preparation of graphitic oxide", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, Vol.15, 1958; p.1339.

- [10] Ami Eitan, Kuiyang Jiang, Doug Dukes, Rodney Andrews, and Linda S. Schadler, "Surface Modification of Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes: Toward the Tailoring of the Interface in Polymer Composites", *Chem. Mater.*, Vol. 15, No. 16, 2003, p. 3198-3201
- [11] Qiu Shilong, Wang Yuting, Wang Chengshuang, Yuan Zuanru, Huang Yu'an, Xie Hongfeng, Cheng Rongshi, "Isothermal Curing Behaviorsof Epoxy/Graphite Oxides Nanocomposites", *Acta Polymerica Sinica*, 1, 2012, p.25-32, DOI: 10.3724/SP.J.1105.2012.11028